

Limits to a Computer's Creativity: Mathematical Proof and Consequences for Big Data

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

In the area of innovation, we are beginning to feel the limits to current Big Data approaches. IBM Watson's limitations have been most discussed regarding its inability to make connections between corpora of information. A recent mathematical proof pinpoints the causes of this limit as well as others expressed about IBM Watson and other Data Science approaches, and points to a different model for the future of Big Data.

2. Aim

To highlight the limits to Data Science's current approaches to innovation and present a new model that overcomes these limits.

3. Conclusions

The new model for innovation is a special human-computer interaction (HCI), *Brain-Swarming*, in which the computer counters every known human obstacle to innovation and the human counters the recently proven computer limitations. The representation used by the *BrainSwarming* HCI is both human- and computer-friendly. Further, the representation is ideal for crowdsourcing by multiple humans. The overall result is a human-computer synergy that is more innovative than either humans or a computer working alone. This approach surpasses the current challenges recently expressed by Data Scientists as well as those limits demonstrated in a mathematical proof.

4. Keywords

innovation, creativity, computational creativity, mathematical proof, human-computer interaction

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Author biography

Dr. Tony McCaffrey Dr. Tony McCaffrey combines the insights from his advanced degrees in cognitive psychology (PhD, UMass Amherst), artificial intelligence (MS, Indiana University), and philosophy (MA, Loyola University Chicago) to advance both human and computer innovative abilities. His research has yielded an effective technique to counter every known human blind spot to creativity. After mathematically proving a limit to a computer's creativity, Tony has designed a human-computer interaction that leverages the strengths of both partners and allows each partner to counter the weaknesses of the other. The result is a human-computer synergy that is more creative than either working alone.

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